

Seven Cognitive Stages of Understanding

Introduction:

Comprehending a thing, a subject, a concept, a new sport or even a person isn't a single-step process; it's a journey. It starts from curiosity to deep understanding is a gradual process, it requires time, effort, and dedicated study.

I've been curious about many things since I was seven. Some of those curiosities stuck, and I took the time to learn and educate myself—thanks mostly to my parents, funding my early interests, and later, my own investment as I grew up. Since 2006, I've studied human behavior both academically and practically, especially in corporate environments. Working for a multinational tech company, I realized that most of the problems I dealt with weren't technical but humane. To put it bluntly, 20% of “uninterested” employees were often responsible for 80% of the issues.

At 16, I made a strange shift from being highly introverted to extroverted, almost overnight. It was like I'd been waiting to be social, but I'd just been around the wrong crowd. Once I felt comfortable, there was no turning back. In the nearly two decades since, I've talked to over a thousand people from all walks of life—engineers, doctors, and professionals from around the world, though notably, no Indian doctors or engineers who mostly got into the field because of family or societal pressure (no joke!).

In these conversations, with people aged 21 to 38 (65% women and 35% men), I found that women, more often than not, were refreshingly honest, whereas men tended to be a bit more reserved. These discussions became the foundation of my hypothesis, revealing patterns in how people move from curiosity to knowledge and eventually, to understanding.

In the last twenty years of my own journey, I've spent almost all those two decades talking to over a thousand people from around the world, understanding them and their approaches to learning things, finding answers to questions and solving simple to complex problems at both work and life. Through these conversations, I've come to realize that there are seven levels of understanding that everyone seems to pass through on their way to the truth of a subject. While individual paths vary, these levels provide a framework to describe how understanding deepens, from casual curiosity to lifelong mastery.

Hypothesis:

I propose that every person on this planet regardless of their social, ethnic or educational background progresses through the following seven levels of understanding or seven cognitive stages, each resulting in a unique guiding question, motivation, and outcome:

Level 1: Curiosity

At this initial level, curiosity sparks from exposure to a new idea—perhaps from a social media post, a friend’s comment, or something seen in passing. Curiosity is casual; it doesn’t demand action. Most people at this stage are merely “window shopping” intellectually, and if their interest doesn’t deepen, they’ll likely move on within a week or less.

Guiding Question: What caught your attention about this topic?

Example Responses:

Male & Female: *“It just looked interesting,” “I wanted to see what it was about.”*

Insight: Curiosity typically arises without specific expectations and is influenced by social or novel triggers, regardless of gender.

Duration: *Typically lasts about a week.*

Level 2: Interest

Curiosity (if last for more than 1 week) is known to develop into interest when there’s reason and some motivation to dig a little deeper. This is where people start dedicating time and energy to understanding a topic or a person. Here, gender may subtly influence motivations: men often cited practical reasons for their interest, while women more commonly expressed an intrinsic draw to the topic or person.

Guiding Question: What made you want to explore this further?

Example Responses:

Male: *“It felt practical or useful.”*

Female: *“I was drawn to the topic and wanted to learn more.”*

Insight: Interest marks the transition from curiosity to active engagement, often reflecting personal or practical relevance.

Duration: *Lasts anywhere from 6 weeks to 6 months.*

Level 3: Knowledge

With sustained interest, people enter the knowledge stage. This is where effort is directed toward learning: books are bought, articles read, and resources gathered. In case of a person of interest, here where you start to dig into their families history, you start looking at old albums and ask the names of their uncles and aunts and cousins. Here, in case of academia gender differences appeared in preferred learning styles, with men leaning toward independent research, while women often preferred community-based or interactive learning.

Guiding Question: *What resources did you turn to first?*

Example Responses:

Male: *“Books, online research.”*

Female: *“Joined a group, talked to people with experience.”*

Insight: *Knowledge acquisition reflects varied learning approaches, showing both individual and social learning preferences.*

Duration: *Lasts between 6 months and 3 years.*

Level 4: Experience

After accumulating knowledge, people enter the experience stage. At this level, they apply what they’ve learned from theory in a real-world setting, often failing and facing unexpected roadblocks and challenges that deepen their understanding. Interestingly, responses from both genders here were remarkably similar, suggesting that the challenges of real-world application transcend gendered perspectives.

Guiding Question: *What keeps you going?*

Example Responses:

Male: *“Making sense of the practical applications was tricky.”*

Female: *“Translating it into real life was a bit of a challenge.”*

Insight: *This stage reinforces commitment and motivates continued learning, often prompting a shift in perspective as theory meets practice.*

Duration: *11 to 33 years.*

Level 5: Mastery

Guiding Question: *When did you start sharing your knowledge with others?*

With experience comes the opportunity for mastery. Mastery isn’t just about knowing a topic inside and out; it’s about teaching and sharing insights with others. Most people hesitate to reach this level, feeling they aren’t “ready,” yet those who do gain an additional layer of understanding by educating others. Mastery is where teaching becomes both an internal and external process, providing value not only to others but to oneself.

Duration: *Begins around 11 years into experience and continues indefinitely.*

Level 6: Speculation

Guiding Question: *What have you found or realized after doing this for such a long time?*

This level arises naturally during mastery when realizations occur unexpectedly. It’s as if, while teaching or deepening one’s practice, new insights appear, leading to speculation about what lies beyond known truths. This stage is marked by critical self-reflection, hypotheses formation, and

even the willingness to challenge foundational beliefs.

Insight: Speculation allows for ongoing growth by questioning and refining understanding, keeping mastery dynamic rather than static.

Duration: *Varies; emerges naturally throughout mastery.*

Level 7: Truth

Guiding Question: *What are the unchanging facts in this field?*

The final level is truth—an irrefutable understanding, like Einstein's $E=mc^2$. Once reached, truth provides a sense of closure and acceptance. For most, this level is the endpoint of understanding in a given subject; it marks the end of inquiry, where the focus shifts to accepting what has been proven.

Conclusion

After two decades of some short and some really lengthy conversations and observations, I developed this Seven stages of understanding or seven cognitive stages framework for understanding the journey from curiosity to truth. While individual paths may differ, these levels describe a consistent pattern in how understanding deepens over time. By examining responses across genders, I've found that both commonalities and subtle differences shape each stage, ultimately enriching the process of learning.

Implications for Further Research:

These findings highlight an area ripe for more structured research. Future studies could explore each level in various fields, examining if and how these patterns hold across different demographics, cultures, or educational backgrounds. This model not only helps map the path to understanding but also shows how learning evolves, adapting as people grow.